

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 101004730

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Evaluation criteria for IFF projects and Evaluation Body

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable reports the activity carried out by WP4 in relation to the organization and implementation of the Internal Innovation Fund. In particular, according to the I.FAST workplan, it is described the definition of the process, the appointment of the Evaluation Committee, the scoring of the projects, and the proposal to GB for award of 8 selected projects.

IFAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The aim of I.FAST WP4 is to define priorities for new innovative developments inside the project, set up and manage an Innovation Fund to support new initiatives in the second phase of the project. The Deliverable D4.1 describes the Innovation management and Committee process.

1. Introduction

The I.FAST Internal Innovation Fund (IIF) is an internal call for projects to be carried out in collaboration with industry during the second phase of I.FAST (years 3 and 4), funded with a budget (EC contribution, total cost) of 1 M€ initially attributed to CERN within WP4, to be redistributed to the selected projects. The Fund aims at stimulating the innovation potential of accelerator technologies, by encouraging I.FAST beneficiaries to identify innovative solutions with viable industrial or commercial potential. This fast-track, competitive process is intended to finance emerging technologies, processes, research, business models and other innovative solutions, at both development and prototype stages.

The I.FAST Governing Board, following a proposal by the Steering Committee, has decided that the IIF will look for intersections of I.FAST thematic areas and EC priority agenda, contributing in tackling similar priorities while connecting accelerator community and society at large. Technologies supported by the IIF shall be capable of advancing the state-of-art within the I.FAST main thematic areas, at the same time contributing to improving the sustainability of particle accelerator technologies. In this context, sustainability corresponds to reducing accelerators' electricity consumption or footprint, or improving their performance for an equivalent impact, or directly preserving the environment thanks to new accelerator-based technologies.

In order to promote new innovative initiatives in the I.FAST community, the process for the selection of the I.FAST Internal Innovation Fund (<https://ifast-project.eu/iif>) projects was defined as below:

- advertise the call inside and outside of the I.FAST project
- organise the Evaluation Board of 10 members from academia and industry
- assess the submitted projects
- pre-select 10 projects and invite them to an in-person pitch at CERN.
- Final selection of projects, considering relative scoring and available budget.

2. IIF Call and Evaluation

The guidelines for the call have been defined by a working group set up by CERN, INFN, and CNRS within I.FAST WP4 and then presented to and approved by the Steering Committee and finally by the Governing Board at its May 2022 meeting. The call for proposals was directed towards the 8 thematic I.FAST areas listed here:

1. Novel particle accelerators concepts and technologies
2. High brightness accelerators for light sources
3. Innovative superconducting magnets
4. Innovative superconducting thin film coated cavities
5. Advanced accelerator technologies and materials
6. Sustainable concepts and technologies
7. Societal applications
8. Technology Infrastructure

The Fund was intended to finance innovative projects at both early development and prototype stages, with technical maturity up to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 4 (validated in laboratory). A financial contribution up to 200 K€ was foreseen, and priority was given in the selection to projects capable of raising additional external funding. It has been decided to have a two-step evaluation process, allowing a start of the activities already at the beginning of 2023, earlier than initially foreseen in the work plan (Annex I). The web page of the IIF (<https://ifast-project.eu/iif>) contains templates, pitch presentation, timeline, selection criteria and guidelines for applications. The Evaluation Board (EvB) was chaired by the WP4 Coordinator and included 10 members: the Project Coordinator ex-officio, the WP3, WP5 and WP9 Coordinators, the Industry Advisory Board (IAB) chair, the INFN and CNRS delegates, a member of the Scientific Advisory Committee, and two representatives from industry, one from an I.FAST industry and one from the Industry Advisory Board. The IIF poster is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Poster of the I.FAST Internal Innovation Fund.

As foreseen by the timeline, the call has been closed on September 15, and at that date 18 projects had applied to receive funding.

3. Management of the innovation fund

The evaluation was managed to guarantee equality of treatment for all the projects, independence and fairness. The evaluators, requested to declare possible conflict of interest, have been asked to evaluate the projects according to the criteria proposed by WP4, discussed in several Steering Committee meetings, and eventually agreed by the Governing Board. The criteria publicly disclosed at the opening of the Call include innovation capacity, impact potential, quality of the projects in term of organisation, use of resources, and schedule. Contribution of the proposed projects to improving sustainability of accelerator technologies was another basic requirement. Eventually a scoring model was disclosed and distributed to the evaluators to make their work easier. At the link below were openly presented the guidelines to the application, the rules of the process, and templates to help preparing the documentation : <https://ifast-project.eu/iif>.

The composition of the EvB as agreed by the Governing Board was as follows:

C. Antoine, CEA, WP9 Coordinator
G. Bisoffi, INFN, WP4 member
M. Baylac, CNRS, WP4 member
A. Faus Golfe, IAB chair
P. Fork, GSI, WP5 Coordinator
R. Geometrante, Kyma SpA (IFAST Beneficiary)
Z. Melhem, Oxford Quantum Solutions Ltd, IAB member
M. Losasso, CERN, WP Coordinator, EvB chair
M. Morandin, INFN, WP3 Coordinator
M. Vretenar, CERN, IFAST Coordinator

The EvB was composed of high-level experts, with a good balance of background (academia and industry), nationality, affiliation, and gender (40% of female members).

At the submission deadline, on September 15th, 18 projects were proposed. The ranking of the projects has been worked out according to the criteria of:

- (a) quality,
- (b) impact,
- (c) implementation,

Each of these criteria had respective sub-criteria:

- (a1) Innovative aspect of the proposal not covered by similar research activity
- (a2) Clarity and Pertinence of the objectives
- (a3) The extent to which the proposed work is beyond the state-of-the-art and demonstrates innovation potential (e.e. ground breaking objectives, novel concepts, and approaches new products and services).

- (b1) The extent to which the outputs of the project would enhance innovation capacity, involve industries and create new market opportunities, strengthen competitiveness and growth of companies or bring other important benefits to society especially in reference to climate change challenges
- (b2) proposed measures to disseminate and exploit the project results, including management of IPR

- (c1) Soundness of the concept, credibility of the proposed methodology in terms of meeting specific market needs. Credibility and soundness of the Industrialization /Business Plan.

(c2) Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, including extent to which the resources assigned to work packages are in line with their objectives and deliverables: credibility and soundness of budget plan and schedule.

(c3) Capability to mobilize additional resources, internal and external to the proposal, for post-IIF implementation and project further follow up and development

After analysing the individual evaluations and rankings of all the proposals made individually by the Evaluators, a consolidated averaged ranking was produced, and at the end of October the first 10 scored projects have been invited to the second round of evaluation with a live presentation at CERN. After the 2nd round of evaluation, following the live presentations, the EvB, in a meeting held on November 25th, has unanimously proposed to the I.FAST Governing Board to endorse the selection of the following 8 projects (please note that the order here does not represent a ranking):

1. Permanent magnet solenoid for High efficiency Klystron (CERN, ELYTT)

Scope of the project is to design and build a permanent magnet solenoid for an available klystron. By increasing the efficiency of the klystrons, it promises to reduce the operational costs of any accelerator together with the associated carbon footprint.

2. High-Temperature High-Gradient Superconductors (CERN, CSIC, CERACO)

Scope of the project is to develop and optimize a 3D coating technology and demonstrate its scalability to make practical RF high power devices. It promises an improvement in Q factor resulting in relevant energy savings for accelerators.

3. Field Emission Cathode for a Travelling-Wave RF gun for High Brightness Beams (PSI, VDL)

Scope of the project is to develop a versatile high brightness MeV electron source based on a field emission cathode. The field emission gun's overall footprint is expected smaller than compared to RF photogun and DC thermoionic gun.

4. KAIO Accelerator (CNRS, CNR)

Scope of the project is to industrially develop a cost- efficient and stable high-power laser technology in the kHz class, apt to be used in radiobiology and testing applications. It promises to reduce energy requirements for Laser Plasma Accelerators.

5. Development of Highly Efficient MW Class Cross Field Vacuum Tube Amplifier for Particle Accelerators Driven by a Solid-State Power Amplifier at 750 MHz (UU)

Scope of the project is to develop a megawatt class cross-field amplifier (CFA) based RF system for particle accelerator applications. It promises the realization of a CFA with peak RF power of 1 MW at 750 MHz with efficiency >80%, gain ~30dB, duty cycle 0.1%.

6. Millisecond flash lamp treatment for SRF accelerating cavities (INFN, HZDR, PICCOLI)

Scope of the project is to develop a novel thermal process to improve performances of superconducting (SC) coating by suppressing (reducing) Cu substrate heating. SC resonant cavities operating at higher T than bulk Nb promise to reduce cryogenic power costs by 60%. In addition, this process is less energy-intensive (20-30%) resulting in a reduction of CO₂ emissions.

7. AM applications of refractory metals for Ion Source cavities (INFN, CNR)

Scope of the project is to develop new Refractory Metals Alloys specifically designed for Additive Manufacturing (AM) to improve the physical performance of the ion sources (Ta-based and/or Nb-based alloys) or to solve the fabrication defects related to pure metals production. It promises to reduce amount of wasted material and increase process efficiency.

8. Demonstration of additive manufacturing for large and complex shaped vacuum chambers by Plasma Metal Deposition (RHP, SBI)

Scope of the project is to demonstrate the Plasma Metal Deposition (PMD) as AM of a large and complex vacuum chamber geometry. It promises a positive impact on the environmental footprint by reduction of material waste by 30 % and more, reduction of integration steps, reduction of stock material, reduction of lead time.

4. Conclusions

The selected projects will be executed by 10 partners that are already I.FAST Beneficiaries, and by 4 new partners (CSIC, CERACO, HZDR, SBI). The IIF Projects will start activities in February 2023, after an electronic vote of the Governing Board to allocated the required funding.